

A New Species of *Stagmomantis* Saussure, 1869 from North America

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Abstract. Recent research has revealed that *Stagmomantis carolina* (Linné, 1763), a taxon that has been historically regarded as a highly variable, single nominal species, actually represents a group of several closely related species. The morphological, biogeographical, and natural history differences of the *Stagmomantis* population found within the Rio Grande Valley region of southern Texas warrant the demarcation of a distinct species apart from *carolina*.

Introduction. As part of a 1942 study concerning the Mantodea and other related insect groups of Texas, Hebard documented the “depauperate” population of *Stagmomantis carolina* in the Brownsville region. Concerning the diminutive members of this population, he remarked:

From no other part of the exceedingly extensive distribution of this species is such extreme depauperation known... Accompanying this depauperation distinctly greater slenderness is shown, but there is too much individual variation generally occurring in the species to permit recognition here even of a geographic race... The presence of adults in the Spring in the Brownsville region indicates a different life cycle in that subtropical environment.

Although Hebard noted the significant differences in habitus morphology and life cycle development between the “*carolina*” of Brownsville and those from other parts of the state/country, he declined to designate the *Stagmomantis* of this isolated region as a distinct species. Given that *carolina* represented a heavily confounded species complex for many years prior to Hebard, his lack of taxonomic action regarding this population was in agreement with the consensus of the time period. However, due to the more precise delineation of *carolina* as detailed by Anderson in 2020, it is necessary to reevaluate the various *Stagmomantis* populations that have been historically aggregated within this species.

Discussion. In addition to the significantly smaller and slenderer habitus characters as noted by Hebard, males from the Brownsville population differ morphologically from *carolina* by having a smaller and slenderer habitus, wider head capsule in relation to supracoxal dilation, shorter forewings, and scant hindwing maculation. Females differ from the type species by having a significantly less marked supracoxal dilation, subfusiform abdomen, and triangular supra-anal plate. Further, whereas *carolina* occurs along the East Coast with a shorter developmental season amid lower winter temperatures, the Brownsville population is restricted to the Lower Rio Grande Alluvial Floodplain in the southern tip of Texas that offers a year-round developmental season amid a subtropical climate. Correspondingly, *carolina* oothecae undergo a 7-9 month diapause over the winter months and have an extended emergence of nymphs in the spring, as compared to Brownsville oothecae that do not require a winter diapause to develop and have a synchronized emergence of nymphs over two broods. Given these morphological, biogeographical, and natural history differences between the two populations, it is warranted to demarcate the Brownsville population as a distinct species, *Stagmomantis resacae* **n. sp.**

References. Linné (1763) pgs 13-14; Serville (1839) pgs 190-191; Scudder (1900) pg 12; Giglio-Tos (1917) pg 54; Giglio-Tos (1927) pgs 379-380; Beier (1935) pg 95; Hebard (1942) pgs 283-285; Anderson (2019) pgs 154-167; Anderson (2020) pgs 9-18; Anderson (2020a) pgs 19-30

A

B

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Stagnomantis rescacae*: A, male holotype dorsal habitus; B, male holotype ventral habitus.
Emerald Point, Hidalgo Co, TX 05.31.20

Voucher Specimen Photographs. C, *Stagmomantis resacae* male holotype (left) vs *Stagmomantis carolina* male (right)

D

Voucher Specimen Photographs. D, *Stagmomantis resacae* male holotype (left) vs *Stagmomantis conspurcata* male (right)

E

F

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Stagmomantis resacae*: E, female allotype dorsal habitus; F, female allotype ventral habitus.
Resaca de la Palma State Park, Cameron Co, TX 10.29.10

G

H

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Stagmomantis resacae*: G, female paratype dorsal habitus; H, female paratype ventral habitus.
Resaca de la Palma State Park, Cameron Co, TX 10.29.10

Voucher Specimen Photographs. I, *Stagmomantis resacae* female allotype (left) vs *Stagmomantis carolina* female (right)

Voucher Specimen Photographs, J, *Stagnomantis rescacae* female allotype (left) vs *Stagnomantis conspurcata* female (right)

Oothecae Photographs. A, *Stagnomantis resacae* oothecae; B, *Stagnomantis resacae* ootheca vertical dissection

Oothecae Photographs. C, *Stagemomantis resacae* ootheca horizontal dissection; D, *Stagemomantis resacae* vacated ootheca with 1 day-old nymph

Oothecae Photographs. E, *Stagmomantis resacae* vacated ootheca; F, *Stagmomantis conspurcata* oothecae (top) vs *Stagmomantis resacae* oothecae (bottom)

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) resacae n. sp.

Type Material. Holotype. 1 ♂ Emerald Point, Hidalgo Co, TX 05.31.20, JConnors. **Allotype.** 1 ♀ Resaca de la Palma State Park, Brownsville, Cameron Co, TX 10.29.10, YSaw. **Paratypes.** 1 ♂ Emerald Point, Hidalgo Co, TX 05.24.20, JConnors; 1 ♂ Emerald Point, Hidalgo Co, TX 06.09.20, JConnors; 1 ♀ Resaca de la Palma State Park, Brownsville, Cameron Co, TX 10.29.10, YSaw. All type specimens are deposited within the author's private collection in Las Vegas, NV.

Description. Habitus of small size, slender in males, more robust in females. General coloration highly variable, ranging from green, brown, tan, or gray, with females most commonly occurring in green phase and males typically grayish-brown. Pigmentation is relatively stable among males, more variable in females with color gradations occurring between highly mottled and nearly monochromatic variants.

Head capsule triangular, quite broad, spanning more than twice as wide as supracoxal dilation. Vertex concave in both sexes, more so in female, placed lower in elevation to dorsal surface of compound eyes. Lower frons broad, spanning 2.5 times as wide as tall, superior margin broadly obtuse-angulate. Compound eyes large, protruding, smooth, ovoid-globular, pigmented either greenish or brown with darker longitudinal striations. Male ocelli quite salient, shining, those of female inconspicuous. Male antennae elongate, nearly reaching base of metazona. Female antennae reaching into distal third of metazona. Antennae filiform, dark brownish-black in both sexes. Head capsule colored same as body color, occasionally with yellow or greenish highlights. Labrum monochromatic.

Pronotum elongated, slender, measuring longer than forecoxae. Supracoxal dilation slight with distal portion of metazona gradually conforming into expansion. Metazona approximately 3 times longer than prozona with salient medial keel, margins subparallel, somewhat constricted before supracoxal dilation, weakly denticulate in female, smooth in male. Prozona wider than metazona but not surpassing supracoxal dilation, margins narrowing toward anterior, weakly armed with dark denticles in both sexes. Coloration of pronotum typically uniform green, brownish, or gray. Light phase individuals may have violet shading with or without darker punctation. Dark phase individuals may also have variable concentration of darker brown or blackish punctation over pronotal surface.

Prothoracic legs slender and elongated. Anteroventral margin of forecoxae armed with 5 uniform-sized, blackish denticles, between which are small serrations of same color as coxae, all of which much more pronounced and stout in female. Posteroventral margin of forecoxae with sparse, minute denticulation. Exterior surface of forecoxae solid green, light brownish with 3 irregular darker brown bands of varying intensity, or light brown with 3 irregular bands of green. Interior surface immaculate. Both sexes with base of forecoxae and surrounding prosternum area blackened. Forefemora bear 4 posteroventral, 14-15 anteroventral, and 4 discoidal spines, all of which are either orange-brown to brownish-black with black tips or having larger anteroventral spines entirely blackened. Tibial spur groove placed in distal half of femora. External surface of forefemora patterned similar to forecoxae by either being solid green, with or without 3 contrasting bands of darker green, or brown with 3 contrasting bands of darker brown or

green, which may be quite faint in some individuals. Internal surface of forefemora typically with small blackish blotches near trochanter, base of discoidal spines, and tibial spur groove, in addition to very faint to strongly contrasting darker bands of body color, as with the external surface. Foretibiae bearing 9-10 posteroventral and 12-13 anteroventral spines, all with black tips. Pigmentation same as body color, transitioning to greenish-orange toward tibial spur in light phase or reddish-brown in dark phase individuals.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, smooth. Pigmentation of female legs variable. Light phase individuals typically have monochromatic green legs with base of femora tinged with violet. Dark phase individuals typically have femora colored same shade as body, annulated with contrastingly darker coloration, with or without green-colored tibiae. Meso/metathoracic legs usually pigmented green regardless of body color in males, often contrasting against the typical grayish-brown of body. Green coloration of femora often transitioning to grayish-brown toward distal apices. Tarsi concolorous with legs, banded with brownish-black at apices or highlighted with violet.

Wings. Male forewings long, narrow, extending to abdominal terminalia or just beyond. Discoidal area hyaline with variable degree of minute, brownish-black maculation; most often entirely immaculate, save stigma. Costal area narrow, roughly one-fifth total width of forewing, entirely hyaline. Stigma consistently dark black, rounded. Female forewings opaque, narrow, extending to abdominal tergite IV. Light phase individuals typically have pigmentation of forewings solid green. Forewings of dark phased individuals are mottled grayish-white to greenish-white with various shades of brown and small amounts of blackish maculations. Costal area spans one-fourth the width of entire forewing. Apices as broad as base, rounded. Stigma conspicuous, deep black in coloration, roundish. Dark phase individuals may have an enlarged, dark black blotch surrounding stigma or have stigma obscured amongst forewing maculation, whereas light phase individuals may have pale blotch surrounding stigma. Male hindwings predominantly hyaline with anal area scantily marked with small cluster of fuscous maculations near posterior margin. Female hindwings narrowly contracted, reduced, anal area solid yellow to reddish-brown at base, tessellated with bands of lemon yellow or reddish-brown cubes against a hyaline or partially infumated background toward outer third. Brownish-black infumation extends throughout entire anal area in some individuals. Discoidal area yellow to reddish-brown. Apices yellowish to greenish or infumated with varying degrees of black.

Abdomen. Male abdomen slender, elongated, pigmented entirely reddish-brown. Female abdomen subfusiform, measuring 5-6.5 mm at widest point, exposing lateral portions of tergites II-IV away from wings. Female supra-anal plate broadly triangular with obtuse apex. Coloration of female abdomen same as body with variable degree of brownish and greenish mottling in dark phase individuals that often concentrates into darkened lateral blotches along tergites IV-VII. Light phase individuals may have yellowish cast to abdominal tergites.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 35.5-44; pronotum length 12-14.5; forewing length 24-32.5; prothoracic coxa length 7-9; prothoracic femur length 8-10; metathoracic femur length 9-12. *Female.* Body length 38.5-47.5; pronotum length 14.5-17; forewing length 13-16; prothoracic coxa length 8-10; prothoracic femur length 10-12; metathoracic femur length 10-11.5.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* elongate-oval in shape, measuring 5-7 mm wide, 10-16 mm long, and 10-12 mm tall. Distal end slightly concave with variable amount of residual process extending away from base; proximal end broadly rounded. Lateral surface ribbed, delimiting approximately 12–15 egg chambers. Eggs within the ootheca are positioned in parallel rows, standing on end, and inclined toward the central furrow. External wall reddish-brown in color with wide, slightly raised, whitish-tan emergence area consisting of 10-22 teardrop-shaped openings placed alternately down center of dorsal surface. These openings are sealed with dried froth until nymph emergence. Thin external coating of tan-colored material typically wears away, revealing the darker brown external wall below. Oothecae are attached along their entire ventral surface so that they sit with the dorsal surface exposed and thus the emergence area is parallel to the substrate. Oviposition sites include woody plant stems and thick twigs.

Development. Nymphs will emerge within 33-51 days of oviposition and do not require a winter diapause to develop. Nymph emergence is synchronized and generally takes place during early morning hours. Proto-nymphs molt embryonic cuticle after threading 3-7 mm past emergence flaps. The liberated first instar nymphs will then disperse away from the ootheca and their siblings. First instar nymphs will begin taking water from droplets within the first day of their emergence. Thereafter they begin feeding upon small prey items, including conspecifics. Older instar nymphs are also highly cannibalistic. Nymphs resemble adults in form and coloration, especially toward later instars. First instar nymphs are yellowish-green in color, gradually turning greenish or brownish within one day of emergence. Pigmentation of early instar nymphs is generally monochromatic with darker punctation and darkened apices of meso/metathoracic femora and tibiae. Body color becomes more variegated as nymphs mature, with darkened leg apices remaining fairly constant. Maturation takes between 87-96 days. Nymphs undergo 7 instars of development before reaching adulthood with an average instar period of 12 days, depending on nutritional intake.

Adulthood. This species is multivoltine, as several generations are produced throughout the year. Nymphs occur with adults from overlapping generations. Adults and nymphs occur among low-lying vegetation, shrubbery, and bushes. Adult males will live for approximately 1 month, whereas adult females may persist nearly 4 months.

Reproduction. Females readily mate 2-3 days after their final molt. Males demonstrate interest in mating 3-5 days after their final molt. Mature males will visually track receptive females for several minutes to a few hours before rapidly pouncing upon them, which may evoke aggression from the female. Males typically mount the female from behind. Occasionally, males will temporarily invert their position while initially mounting atop the female to seemingly examine the female's genitalia. They will then right themselves and continue clinging onto her body or may immediately initiate copulation. Mating generally lasts for 8-10 hours but occasionally spans 1-2 days. Cannibalism during mating regularly occurs. Surviving males will typically fly away. Males may also remain mounted to the female after copulation has been discontinued, which further endangers them to cannibalism regardless of the female's appetite. Both sexes may mate multiple times with the same partner or with different conspecifics. Mated females oviposit their first ootheca between 3-5 days post-copulation and during this time will be unreceptive to males. Oviposition generally takes place at night. Females will continue to produce a new ootheca every 10 days after their first

oviposition, depending on food availability. Mated females are capable of producing up to 11 oothecae that contain between 28-55 eggs each before succumbing to age after 3-4 months of adult life. When multiple oothecae are generated, those that are produced toward the end of the female's life tend to be smaller and are more likely to be infertile. Unmated females will produce infertile oothecae between 25-30 days after final molt. These infertile oothecae are of roughly the same size and shape as viable ones.

Ethology. Adult males are attracted to lights at night and frequent UV/mercury vapor lamps. Adult females have been observed to inhabit vegetation within close proximity of each other, occasionally having several individuals cohabiting the same plant just inches apart. Adult cannibalism among this species has not been indicated, outside of mating. Adult females may respond to threats with a deimatic display that involves facing the aggressor, unfurling both wings above body, partial abdominal dorsiflexion and outward extension of forelegs.

Narrative. During 2010-2011, Saw conducted a study of Mantodea found within Resaca de la Palma State Park in Cameron County, Texas, wherein several live samples of female *Stagmomantis* were retained following a field assessment of species diversity in the region. The female specimens that Saw retained oviposited oothecae within captivity. The subsequent broods were successfully reared for a complete generation. Saw meticulously documented the life cycle of this species, which was thought at the time to be an aberrant population of *carolina*.

Saw discussed the findings of his study with the present author in 2020, ten years after its completion. Saw, a longtime resident of southern Texas who has extensive experience with Mantodea husbandry, reported that he has routinely collected mantises throughout the region for many years and has encountered “this smaller version of *carolina* only at this specific state park located in Resaca de la Palma at Brownsville, nowhere else.” He went on to report that “out of the park and just across the bridge” the larger *conspurcata* can be found, suggesting that the two species may not co-occur within the park itself.

Diagnosis. This species is diagnosable among *Stagmomantis* males by having a smaller and slenderer habitus (body length measuring 35.5-44 mm in *resacae* vs 46-52 mm in *carolina*), wider head capsule in relation to supracoxal dilation (supracoxal dilation width over head capsule width 2.17 in *resacae* vs 1.56 in *carolina*), shorter forewings (24-32.5 mm in *resacae* vs 33.5-36 in *carolina*), and scant hindwing maculation. This species is diagnosable among *Stagmomantis* females by having narrower forewings (length over width at middle 3.50-3.88 in *resacae* vs 2.86-3.67 in *carolina*), hindwings narrowly contracted/reduced, abdomen subfusiform (measuring 5-6.5 mm at widest point in *resacae* vs 9.5-11 in *carolina*), and broadly triangular supra-anal plate.

Etymology. *resacae* is the Latinized derivative of resacas—the ancient lakes and former channels of the Rio Grande found throughout the Rio Grande Valley region of Cameron County, Texas and Resaca de la Palma State Park, a unique biogeographical area of the country where this species was first documented.

References. Saw (2011a) pgs 4-55; Anderson (2020) pgs 9-18; Saw (2020) pers. comm.

U.S./Canadian Distribution Range of *Stagemomantis resacae*

01, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult male holotype. Emerald Point, Hidalgo Co, TX 05.31.20

02, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult male paratype. Emerald Point, Hidalgo Co, TX 05.24.20

03, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult female. Resaca de la Palma State Park, Cameron Co, TX
12.03.16

04, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult female. Sabal Palm Sanctuary, Cameron Co, TX
11.27.16

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult male holotype
Photographed by Joseph Connors

02, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult male paratype
Photographed by Joseph Connors

03, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult female
Photographed by Jeff Gruber

04, *Stagmomantis resacae* adult female
Photographed by Jeff Gruber

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